

**BARRIERS TO ADOPTION OF NEW PUBLIC MANAGEMENT TOWARDS
INNOVATION:
A CASE STUDY OF PHILIPPINE COCONUT AUTHORITY REGIONAL OFFICE XI**

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ABSTRACT

The case study aimed to identify the barriers in Philippine Coconut Authority Regional Office XI that deter the adaption to new practices of public management. The primary data were congregated using key-informant interview of the selected five (5) personnel from the different units of the agency. The data were analyzed and construed by thematic content analysis. Results of the case study showed that age, collaboration, reform of processes, status of employment and technology were the identified barriers that deter the adaption to new practices of public management of PCA R.O XI. The case study concluded that though some of the practices of new public management are observed in the agency, there is still a need for reforms and improvements in order to meet the agency's goals, missions and targets.

Keywords:

Reform, new public management practices, technology, collaboration, status of employment, case study

INTRODUCTION

The rapid social, economic, technological change and the effects of globalization make the government struggle thus creating the need for reform of public management practices. Public sector and systems need considerable renewal and even reform because of the risks, unknown complexity and unpredictability in the future.

New public management can be defined as a new set of experiments in public sector management informed with the market principles of efficiency and economy to make ailing public sector effective. New public management calls for a paradigm shift in public sector management informed with three E's — Efficiency, Economy and Effectiveness. New public management involves changing trend in government growth shifting towards administrative reforms, developing automation and internationalizing (Riaz-Ud-Din, 2017).

However, as observed in PCA R.O XI, there are still existing practices that are old instead of adopting the new public management practices. Examples of these are the use of Daily Time Record (DTR) cards instead of biometrics, the practice of using electronics to promote "paperless" transactions, the use of typewriters in some forms though there are computers provided, the manual encoding of the agency's expenditures and transactions where in fact there are software applications available in the market and the lack of collaboration by the agency to the coconut farmers and other government and private sectors which if given attention can help the agency achieve its goals.

Anchored in the salient features of new public management as cited by Riaz-Ud-Din (2017), this case study intended to identify the gaps that hinder the adaption of new public management practices in PCA R.O XI.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The main objective of this case study was to identify the barriers that hinder the adaptation to new practices of public management in Philippine Coconut Authority R.O XI. The identified difficulties can be the reason for the management to become outmoded.

METHODOLOGY

This case study was conducted at PCA R.O XI located at PCA Complex, Bago Oshiro, Tugbok District, Davao City and employed the qualitative method. Qualitative research is used to gain understanding of underlying reasons, opinions and motivations. It is also used to uncover trends in thought and opinions, dive deeper into the problem. Common methods include focus group discussions, individual interviews and participation/observations. Moreover, sample size is typically small and respondents are selected to fulfil a given quota (DeFranzo, 2011). A total of Five (5) personnel representing the five (5) units of the agency 1.) Administrative Unit, 2.) Accounting Unit, 3.) Supply Unit, 4.) Cashier Unit and 5.) Technical Unit were the key-informants of this study. According to the Encyclopedia of Survey Research Methods (2008), key-informant interviews are in-depth interviews of a select (non-random) group of experts who are the most knowledgeable of the organization or issue. They are often used as part of program evaluation and needs assessments, though they can also be used to supplement survey findings, particularly for the interpretation of survey results. Thematic content analysis was used to analyze the data gathered. Thematic content analysis enables researchers to develop a deeper appreciation for the group or situation they are researching. Researchers determine broad patterns that will allow them to conduct more granular research and analysis (Komori, N.D).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are the barriers to adaption of new public management practices in the Philippine Coconut Authority, Regional Office XI as revealed in the study:

Age

In PCA R.O XI, it is proven that age can deter the adaption to practices of new public management because according to PCA R.O XI Personnel Complement Report as of October 2018, half of the total number of employees belonged to the 35-65 age bracket. This means that they are more resistant to change in terms of the new technologies.

There are five (5) widespread beliefs of age-related issues. First, age and job performance are increasing in importance. Second, there is a mixed perception among employees. Some employers perceived that older workers have more experience, better judgment, a strong work ethic and commitment to quality. Others perceived that older workers are more resistant to change especially on new technology, and still other believed that the older you get, the less likely you are to quit your job. Third belief is that age is inversely related to absenteeism. Older employees have lower rates of avoidance of absence but have a higher rate of unavoidable absence, maybe due to poor health associated with age. Fourth is the widespread belief that productivity declines and individual skills decay over time with age. Lastly, relationship between age and job satisfaction is mixed. Some studies showed a positive association between age and job satisfaction, at least up to age 60 (business.fulletron document, 2007).

Weak Collaboration

Though it has always not done well, collaboration has always been a function of good governance. As time passes by, things have changed. There are just more people to talk with and many more spaces in which to do both. These situations weaken the pace of collaboration to happen.

Based on the result, it is observed that there is a need for improvement in collaboration of PCA R.O XI to other government agencies and private sectors. Some projects of the agency are not well disseminated to the public particularly the coconut farmers. PCA R.O XI need to massively upgrade the capacity to connect, to communicate, and to collaborate. Embracing the new instincts, culture, and capabilities of "connectedness" is needed by the agency to meet the new demands it confronts. It is increasingly the human networks of knowledge, people and communities that will drive innovation for economic resilience, social inclusion, and environmental sustainability.

Local governments do not stand alone – they find themselves in new relationships not only with state and federal government, but often with a widening spectrum of other public and private organizations as well. The result of this reforming of local governments calls for a new collaborations and managerial responses that occur in addition to governmental and bureaucratic processes-as-usual, bringing locally generated strategies into play (Agranolf, et.al, 2004).

In a report from Pew Research Center's Internet and American Life project, the link was made explicitly between the quality of community information systems and to how people feel about the quality of government

and civic institutions. In a local government context, the report presents research that suggest that open and accessible public data has an impact on the way people think about their public agencies. The report concluded that those who think local government does well in sharing information are also more likely to be satisfied with other parts of civic life such as the overall quality of their community and the performance of government and their institutions, as well as the ability of the entire information environment in the community to give the information that matters.

Long and Bureaucratic Processes

Government designs and delivers services. It is one of the primary ways in which its works impact people and communities. However, in the case of PCA R.O XI, there are steps in the processing of documents that tend to be repetitive therefore making the transaction processes to take longer. Addressing systematic issue requires changes to back office policy and service systems as well as the innovative use of technology to draw together and present the services in a meaningful way to users and at the same time to simplify and integrate the processes across different providers. This includes the role of technology, social media, and the mix of public, private and civil society organizations involved.

According to the recent report of Fostering Innovation in the Public Sector (2017), innovation in the public sector is hard to achieve. The scale and nature of the challenges that government face today require responses that go beyond simply incremental improvements and towards radically shifting the gears of government, towards empowering individuals to achieve outcomes and not just delivering processes. It also stated that innovation also needs adaption to context, and flexibility of execution.

Status of Employment

Results of the in-depth interview showed that those who are in Contract of Service and Job Order status of employment are less likely to welcome the adaption of new public management practices and prefer to be neutral in the sense that it is fine if new practices are introduced but it is still fine if they practice what is normally done. In addition, those who are holding regular positions in the agency belong in the 35-65 years of age, the age bracket who are more resistant to change in terms of the new technologies. Both the age and status of employment contribute a lot in explaining why until now there are still old practices of public management in the agency.

Employees' length of service and their status are believed to have a relationship with work performance. Employees with a long period of continued full-time employment may find themselves in a better position to grow and obtain more responsible positions (Brauchle and Azam, 2004).

Outdated Information Technology

Technology is one of the hindrances in adapting the new public management practices of PCA R.O XI because though there are computers present, these technologies are not up to date. Moreover, the agency has only one (1) IT personnel and the said person does other jobs resulting to lesser focus for the improvement of technologies in the office.

An article from the Online Master of Public Administration program of University of Francisco entitled "The Impact of Emerging Technology on Management and Public Administration" stated that many of the emerging technologies that influence public administration fall under the broad heading of IT (Information Technology). The term includes any technology, software or hardware used to transmit, store and manipulate information in the form of data. Having more efficient IT infrastructure equipped with new technologies allows public administration system to get more work done faster and more securely even when employees are on the go.

Government reform and public service performance improvement is impossible without an enthusiastic embrace of the new tools and networks of technology-enabled communications and collaboration which are enabling, a more open and connected world.

CONCLUSION

Following the salient feature of new public management as stated by Riaz-Ud-Din (2017), PCA R.O XI can change its practices to improve the agency's performance. Adapting to the new public management practices will open a door for development in the agency thus helping the organization achieve its goals, missions and targets. Lastly, in this fast and changing environment, the organization needs to adapt to new practices to be able to stay on track.

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